

This is the README file for the *Lifecycle Greenhouse Gas Emissions of Raw Steel Production Plants in the U.S.* study. The following includes descriptions of data, code, and results used for data analyses and visualizations for the paper.

Reach out to mayfield@dartmouth.edu or xinyue.zou.th@dartmouth.edu if there are any additional questions.

Folder 'code' includes the input data and code for the study.

'LCA_steel_emission_v2.py' is the Python file we used for this study. To run the model, one should download the Python file, required packages, and the 'Master_Workbook_updated.csv' and 'road_distances.json'

'Master_Workbook_updated.csv' is the iron and steel industry database we used for this study.

More information about the 'Master_Workbook_updated.csv' can be found in the 'Master_Workbook Documentation.rtf'.

'road_distances.json' is the pre-calculated distance file between upstream and downstream plants. To re-calculate the file, one should run the 'travel_distance.py' Python file in the 'Additional files' folder.

Additional files 'road_distances.json' and 'travel_distance.py' are pre-calculated distance files between upstream and downstream plants which were used in the 'LCA_steel_emission_v2.py' to expedite the computational speed.

Additional files 'BF-BOF.csv', 'Coal-Coke.csv', 'Coke/BF Grade Pellet-BF.csv', 'DR Grade Pellet/DRI.csv' and 'DRI/Scrap-EAF.csv' are the documentations and references for material and energy intensity-related parameters we used in the python file.

Additional files 'GEM_EAF_share.csv', 'GEM_plant_production.csv', 'GEM_US_plant_updated' and 'resource_mix_2022' are files used to update the previous 'Master_Workbook.csv' to the current 'Master_Workbook_updated.csv'.

Folder 'result_updated' provides the results and visualizations.

'results.csv' is the plant-level emissions from the model run. More information about the 'results.csv' can be found in the 'results documentation.rtf'.

'Figure 2' and 'Figure 3' are the visualizations plotted by the code. 'Figure 2' is the plant-level direct and lifecycle emissions supply-curve plot. 'Figure 3' is the plant-level emissions breakdown plot.

'bf_bof_transport_matrix.csv', 'bf_pellet_transport_matrix.csv', 'coke_transport_matrix.csv', 'dr_pellet_transport_matrix.csv' and 'iron_eaf_transport.csv' are the intermediate network optimization results generated by the model.

The optimization results are structured in matrices, Column As are the product producer's plant names and the rest of the columns are the product consumer's plant names. Values represent the quantity of product from producer to consumer.

Additional files 'abstract_art.py' and 'abstract_art.png' are the code and figure for the cover arts, based on model results.

Additional files 'sankey.py' and 'snakey.html' are the code and figure for the sankey diagram in the manuscript, based on model results.

Additional files 'EPD_plot.py', 'EPD_results_updated.csv', 'EPD_results.csv', and 'EPD_comparison.png' are the code and input for the EPD vs study figure in the manuscript. 'EPD_results.csv' are the reported plant-level EPD data gathered from public information and 'EPD_results_updated.csv' compiled the model results with the reported EPD data for each plant.

File 'results_clean_v2.csv' provides the downloadable results with column names and units. This file is cleaned based on the 'results.csv' file in the 'results_updated' folder, for easy access to the results.